

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B406

Date: 25th September 2008

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
083958		!	-.18 kft	129	start engines
084244		!	-.18 kft	129	ASPs open
084307		!	-.19 kft	129	start taxi
084925		T/O	0.64 kft	352	from Cranfield
085402		!	7.8 kft	317	Nevzorov/JW zero
091141		!	18.0 kft	309	Nevzorov/JW zero
091739	093730	Profile 1	18.0 - 0.5 kft	277	
092831		!	7.0 kft	275	Heimann cal
093250		Profile 1	2.4 kft	228	change to 500fpm
093725		!	0.9 kft	220	retract bbr cover
093742	100748	Run 1	0.5 kft	186	QNH 1034
094056		!	0.5 kft	182	
094208		!	0.5 kft	180	Heimann cal
094539		!	0.5 kft	178	Heimann turned off/on
100749	101502	Profile 2	0.5 - 5.5 kft	170	
101217		!	2.6 kft	140	change to 1000fpm
101502	102028	Profile 3	6.0 - 0.5 kft	141	
102029	102555	Profile 4	0.5 - 2.4 kft	144	
102608	103703	Run 2	2.5 - 3.0 kft	132	
102743		!	2.5 kft	133	Nevzorov/JW zero
103147		!	2.6 kft	134	Nevzorov/JW zero
103703	104225	Profile 5	2.6 - 0.5 kft	134	
104236	105909	Run 3	0.5 kft	087	
105920	110702	Profile 6	0.24 - 6.5 kft	058	
110709	111640	Profile 7	6.4 - 0.10 kft	046	
111655	112522	Run 4	0.5 kft	089	
111851		!	0.5 kft	087	Nevzorov/JW zero
112544	113122	Profile 8	0.21 - 4.5 kft	085	
113127	114213	Run 5	4.5 kft	087	
114222	115022	Profile 9	4.5 - 0.5 kft	058	500 fpm profile
115050	121844	Run 6	0.5 kft	017	
115324		!	0.5 kft	016	Heimann cal
121854	123051	Profile 10	0.5 - 10.0 kft	344	
125611		Land	0.0 kft	211	Cranfield

ADIENT Flight B406: Fresh vs aged aerosol

FAAM Sortie Brief

Thursday, September 25, 2008

Operating areas: Over coastal areas around Britain downwind of EU and UK pollution sources. FAAM waypoints indicated below. NOTAM required for Irish Sea (Liverpool plume area)

Weather: No rainfall. Easterly conditions. Some low cloud.

Sortie Summary: A round Britain sortie to survey the UK aerosol budgets upwind and downwind of sources. After Transit across north Britain, plume work in Irish Sea (NOTAM required) followed by 500ft round Britain (anticlockwise) to East Anglia.

Flight Patterns:

- 1) If clear skies at Cranfield (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
- 2) Take off Cranfield 10:00 L (9:00Z) and transit at midlevel towards point A (53°30 N, 3°30)W, in Irish Sea, just north of North Wales. [50mins, T=50]
- 3) Broken profile descent in this region to 500ft at 1000 ft per min above 3000 ft and 500 ft per min below 3000 ft. [15 min, T=65]
- 4) Perform a raster pattern consisting of a series of 10 min SLRs at 500ft (or within aerosol layer). SLRs oriented N-S or as appropriate across plume, raster pattern moving west as conditions allow (to be decided by mission scientist). [60mins, T=120]
- 5) Begin round Britain sortie at 500ft using suggested routing via waypoints [50min, T=170]
52, 51, 50, 49, 48 (western section)
- 6) Crossing Cornwall at 2000ft or appropriate altitude. Resume 500ft level and continue anticlockwise along S coast and around SE coast of Britain [100 min, T=270]
46, 45, 44, 43, 42, 41, 40 (southern section)
- 7) If time, perform a profile ascent to 5000ft between waypoints 40 and 87 in the vicinity of Weybourne. [10 mins, T=280]
- 8) Resume to FL110 for transit back to Cranfield
- 9) Recover to Cranfield [20,min, T= 300]
- 10) Perform pirouette as in step #1

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.406** Date **Sept 25** Name **Megan Northway** Page **1** of **3**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
8:45Z		0 ft			early T10 7/8 strCu at cranfield nozy
8:59Z					Strong inversion
9:02Z	Transit B	FL180			a lot of ^{high} str. Cu: below. Approaching WAH - waseca
9:17:39	PI	FL180			Descending Towards #52 cloud tops around 5 5 kft thin also stratus layer.
9:29	PI				hazy below clouds. - low visibility.
9:37:25	end of PI				
9:37:42	start RI				500ft Neph 50 m
"	"	500ft			Smooth over water.
"	"	"			not much NO ₃ - mostly SO ₄ + org
"	RI	500ft			wet neph hygrometer saturating - not much use!
10:04:00	RI	500ft			aerosol has dropped off
10:07:49	end RI				near pt 50

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.406** Date **25 Sept** Name **Megan Northrup** Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:07:49	P2	500ft - 6kft		near 451	(sawtoothing) profiling up to 6kft at 451
	P3				(slow)
	P4				and again to 3kft over Corn- wall
10:26:08	R2	3000ft			over land lots of plumes over land
10:30:03	P5	3000ft - 500ft			- Descending into cloud - dark wall - may not get down.
10:39	P5	"			large plume again on this side near pt 46.
10:42:36	R3	500ft			ship plume ^{- starboard (right)} with high CN + smps bimodal
"	"	"			98% RH amb. - NO3 not dominant as it was in winter.
	P6	500 - 7kft			Sawtooth to 7 kft. btwn 45 + 44
11:07:02	P7	7kft - 500ft			back down to 500ft
11:16	"	"			passing Isle of Wight, pt 44.
11:16:40	R4	500ft.			- ship plume -
11:25:44	end R4	500ft			clear skies above now.
	start P8				profile ascent to 4500 ft
	R5	4500ft			Run at 4500ft
11:42:20	P9	4500 - 500ft			Profile descent to 500ft
11:44	"	"			(went through cloud)
					crossing pt 42

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.406** Date **25/11/08** Name **GRANT ALLEN** Page **1** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08:40		0 m		Croyfield	Ground conditions: Boundary layer cu (5/8) clearing. High vis. Low E winds. 15°C. 1020 mb (rising)
08:49		0 m		"	T/O + Transit to A (53°30'N, 3.30W)
08:52		1000m		"	CB cleared. No high level cloud.
08:54		850mb		"	Strong T inversion at 1500m (850mb) > 6°C. Pollution likely to be capped at 850mb.
					T/O RH = 98%. T inversion = 70%
08:59					Neph shows cap at 5000ft.
09:05					SL at 18kft (505mb) T = -14°C. RH ~ 75%.
					Low level St cu all the way.
09:17	1	18kft	W	WP54	Start of descent. 1000ft/min towards WP52

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.406** Date 25/1/03 Name GRANT ALLEN Page 2 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:24	1	Descending	W	54 → 52	Clear on descent
09:27	1	"	"	"	Some high level Cirrus.
09:30	1	"	"	"	Entering cloud. (850ms)
					5000 ft. Same cap level.
09:31			SW		Turn to SW. Descending 500ft/min
09:37	1	500ft.	S	52 → 51	Start of 500ft run.
09:40	1	"	"	"	Passing out of strong NW (Manchester) plume at 53°N.
09:53	1	500ft.	S	51	Arrive WPS1.
10:07	1	500ft.	S	51 → 50	Increase in NO _x , decrease on neph. Possible aged plume. AMS reported reduction in NO ₃ .
10:05	1	500ft.	S	51 → 50	End of NO _x plume.
10:08	2	Ascending	SE	50	Start of profile ascent to 6000ft.
10:15	3	Descending	SE		Profile descent from 6000ft.
10:25	4	Ascending	SE	48	Overland SE at 2400ft
					Local plumes evident on ascents and descents showing increases in NO _x , NO ₃ (AMS) and O ₃ .
10:30	4	2400ft	SE	48 → 46	Some turbulence. NO _x ~ 3ppbv. Neph stable (20m ⁻¹) Some local spikes (over land)
10:37	5	<	SE	48 → 46	Profile descent to 500ft now clear of land.

Mission Scientist's Log

DigiMemo e-Page

Flight No **B.406** Date **25A/08** Name **GRANT ALLEN** Page **3** of **4**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:42	Run 3	500ft.	E	56745	500 ft run.
					ENTERING Strong plume *
					NO_x NO _x went from 3 → 8
					ppbv! O ₃ went from 30 → 10
					ppbv, indicating O ₃ destruction
					on high NO _x . AMS
					reporting high NO ₂ too.
10:47	"	"	"	"	NO _x peaks at 12 ppbv!
					O ₃ troughed at 12 ppbv
					1/3 of NO _x is NO indicating
					fresh plume. AMS reports
					strong NO ₂ signal for past 5
					mins.
10:51					Passed over ship plume *
					CNC and SO ₄ (AMS) saw
					spikes. (NO and NO _x anti-correlated)
10:59	6	>	NE	45	Profile ascent to 6000ft -
					Sampled plume well. Plume
					was just ending (O ₃ >, NO _x <)
					as we started the climb.
11:07	7	<	NE	45 → 44	Profile descent from 6000ft -
11:18	Run 4	500ft.	E	44 → 43	SL at 500ft.
11:17	4	500ft	E	"	Plume entered. Negh (50 m ⁻¹)
					NO _x > 10 ppbv, O ₃ < 20 ppbv.
					Clear skies.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B406

Date: 25 sep 08

Operator: JC

Page 1 of 3

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> 080000 time set on cip, ffssp & precip precip checked for disc space </div>											
<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px;"> 085800 post take off ffssp recording and auto, ref 3.2V 5.0/4.9/-4.4V 2dp off 2dc on pcasp heater on, vreff before take off > 7.5, now 7.3. flow 0.8 before take off </div>											
091600	24	0.09	1	Not fitted	0	0		Not operated			FI 180 in transit
091739	20	0.07	1		0	0					FI180 start p1, clear air
091950	50	0.09	1		0	0					FI160
092348	45	0.09	1		0	0					FI120
092546	45	0.08	1		0	0					FI100
092930	100	0.09	1		0	0					FI060
093100	286	0.09	84		0	0					FI040 thin cloud layer
093330	632	0.09	84		0	0					FI020
093726	1500	0.09	85		0	0					FI000 end p1
											Start r1 at 500ft
094500	960	0.1	87		0	0					Pcasp vref 7.0, flow 0.7
095000	870	0.09	89		0	0					2dc el#1 -1.5, el#32 -1.0
											Cip - no display
095500	928	0.09			0	0					

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B406

Date: 25 sep 08

Operator: JC

Page 2 of 3

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
100000	756	0.09	90		0	0					
100500	900	0.09	91		0	0					
100745	770	0.09	91		0	0					End ri start p2, f1000
	355	0.09	91		0	0					FI010
	360	0.09	91		0	0					FI020
	280	0.09	91		0	0					FI030
	3000	0.06	200		0	0					FI050 thin cloud layer
	34	0.08	207		0	0					FI060 end of p2 start p3
	40000	0.06	358		0	0					FI045 thin cloud layer
	420	0.1	362		0	0					FI030
	650	0.09	362		0	0					FI010
102025	800	0.1	362		0	0					End p3 start p4
102557	450	0.1	362		0	0					End p4 start run 2
103000	460	0.09	400		0	0					
103500	440	0.1	410		0	0					
103700	520	0.1	410		0	0					End run 2 start p5
104020	822	0.1	410		0	0					Just entering cloud
104227	845	0.1	416		0	0					End p5 start run 3
104500	950	0.1	418		0	0					
105000	930	0.1	421		0	0					
105500	900	0.1	423		0	0					
105910	873	0.1	425		0	0					End run 3 start p6
	394	0.1	425		0	0					FI010
	330	0.1	425		0	0					FI020
	41000	0.08	564		0	0					FI055 thin cloud layer
110702	64	0.09	564		0	0					End p6 start p7
	10000	0.08	596		0	0					FI048
	513	0.08	596		0	0					FI023
111638	1000	0.09	597		0	0					End p7 start run 4
112000	914	0.09	598		0	0					
112523	1300	0.1	599		0	0					End run 4 start p8
113122	387	0.1	599		0	0					End p8 start run 5

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B405**
ADIENT

Date 25 sept 08

Page 1 of .. operator

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	$B_a \times 10^{-6}$	Ph_det levels		Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time: done 054950Z	New filter Tr = 1.000 done	Set to 3.0 lpm: N/A	15.4	18	47	Ave =30 s	←Preflight
074000	1.0			18	45		Preflight OK/Filter in/pump off.
091739	1.0	2.36 at FL170		18	44		start P1 descent. Pump On. RS232 logging start.
093014							pump Off for Clouds
092324	1.0	2.56		18	44		pump on at 3000ft
101402	0.94	2.56		17	44		pump off at 4400ft
101435							pump on
101605							pump off
101717							pump on
102550	0.929			16	44		pump off
104847							pump on
110535							pump off
110610							pump on
110825							pump off
111030							pump on
114620							pump off
114759							pump on
130240	0.684			12	44		pump off. DATA STOP

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.406**

 Date **25/9/08**

 Operator's name: **A. Wilson**

 Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
074000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	PREFLIGHT OK. CHILLER FILLED.
092415	P1 ↓	FL110	10.5	11.2	35.3	-	-	WET NEPH DATA START.
092900	P1 ↓	FL060	12.5	24.3	38.4	↗	20	CHILLER ON. SET RH TO 85% FOR DESCENT TO 500FT. ^{Heater on.}
093742	R1/R1	500ft	15.0	59.2	88	↘	42	END P1/START R1 @ 500FT. RAMPING DOWN. AMS reports Sulphates & organics.
094610	R1	500ft	15.0	67*	64	↗	18	RAMP UP. DRY NEPH RH LOOKS SUSPECT. (Approx 20% RH 700ft high)
095305	R1	500ft	15.1	62.1	94.5	↘	44	RAMP DOWN.
100330	R1	---	---	53.6	60.1	↗	15	RAMP UP.
100749	R1/R2	500ft	15.0	53	91	→	44.5	END R1/R2 Run 1/START P2 ↗ 600ft.
101027	P2	1500ft	14.1	43.5	93.8	↘	45	SET RH TO MIN DURING PROFILE ASCENT & DESCENT.
101502	P2/P3	6000ft	12.8	23	64	↘	23.9	
102029	P3/P4	500ft	14.8	52	55	→	44.6	END P3/START P4 ↗ 300ft TO CROSS CORNWALL.
102555	P4/R2	3000ft	13.9	39.9	44.8	→	8.5	END P4/START P2 ACROSS DEERAN/CORNWALL/500ft.
103703	R2/R5	3000ft ↓	14.0	39	39.1	→	8.3	END R2/START P5 BACK TO 500ft.
104150	R5	600ft		62	45	↗	8.3	RAMP UP.
104236	R3	500ft	15.0	62	48	↗	19.8	START R3
104650	---	500ft	14.0	63	84	↗	43	SET FLOW TO 14
105100	---	---	10	65	91.6	→	45	SET FLOW TO 10
105440	---	---	16	65	93	↘	46	RAMPING DOWN + FLOW UP. GOOD GROWTH LAST RUN.
105920	R3/R6	500ft ↗	16	59	87	↘	25.2	END RUN 3/START PROFILE ↗ FL070
110702	P6/P7	7000ft	13.6	6.7	40.3	↘	11.2	END P6/START P7

B406_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

07:16:30.90 --- - - - -
07:16:30.90 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
07:16:30.90 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
07:16:30.90 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B406
07:16:30.90 --- - - - -
07:16:37.87 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
07:16:41.22 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
07:16:41.78 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
07:16:45.97 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:16:47.46 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:16:50.03 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:16:51.46 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:16:54.08 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
07:16:55.45 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
07:16:58.13 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:16:58.22 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:17:06.22 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
07:17:36.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:17:36.31 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:17:36.33 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:17:45.79 LSH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:17:45.79 LSH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:17:49.32 USH - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:17:49.33 USH - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:17:51.72 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:17:51.73 SWS - - - 40 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
07:18:21.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:21.32 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:18:21.91 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:25.61 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:18:30.58 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:31.43 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:32.64 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:33.47 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:34.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:35.60 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:39.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:40.74 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:42.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:43.17 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:45.44 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:18:46.29 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:18:55.07 LSH - - - - Idling
07:18:55.09 USH - - - - Idling
07:18:55.15 SWS - - - - Idling
07:35:35.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:35.56 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:35.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:48.44 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:35:49.28 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:51.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:35:51.59 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:35:52.18 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:53.63 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:35:53.91 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
07:35:54.51 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:35:57.42 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
07:36:01.53 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:36:02.38 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:36:03.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:36:04.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:36:06.42 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:36:07.26 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:36:08.86 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
07:36:09.70 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
07:36:10.76 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

07:36:11.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:12.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:13.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:14.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:15.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:16.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:17.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:36:19.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:36:20.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:42.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:42.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:44.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:45.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:46.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
07:42:47.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
07:42:50.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:50.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
07:42:50.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
08:30:50.53	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 94.996
08:30:51.65	SWS	95.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:33:13.28	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
08:33:13.29	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 100ms.
08:35:56.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:56.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:56.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:57.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:00.37	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:36:04.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:05.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:06.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:07.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:07.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:08.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:09.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:11.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:36:11.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:36:12.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:06.58	SWS	95.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
08:51:06.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:51:07.67	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:51:14.61	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:51:18.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:19.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:20.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:21.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:22.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:23.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:28.23	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
08:51:28.23	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
08:51:30.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:31.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:33.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:34.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:35.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:36.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:37.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:38.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:39.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:41.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:42.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:51:44.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:51:45.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
08:53:11.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 8 deg
08:54:16.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
08:55:08.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
08:55:56.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
08:59:32.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
09:01:16.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

09:01:17.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:18.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:19.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:19.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:20.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:43.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:44.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:45.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:45.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:47.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:48.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:51.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:51.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:52.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:53.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:05:54.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:05:55.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:08:55.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
09:09:07.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
09:09:47.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
09:10:55.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:56.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:57.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:58.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:10:58.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:10:59.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:12:35.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
09:13:05.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
09:15:52.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
09:16:57.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:16:58.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:16:59.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:17:00.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:17:01.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:17:02.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:17:02.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:17:42.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
09:17:57.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 1
09:24:33.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
09:24:42.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
09:25:49.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
09:30:10.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 10 deg
09:30:49.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
09:31:12.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** going through cloud
09:35:03.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
09:37:33.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1 at 500
09:37:40.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 500 ft
09:37:46.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:47.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:47.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:48.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:37:49.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:37:50.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:25.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:26.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:28.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:28.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:30.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:31.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:09.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:11.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:12.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:13.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:14.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:30.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:00:31.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:32.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:32.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:00:33.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:00:34.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:00:35.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:09.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:09.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:10.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:11.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:03:12.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:03:13.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:46.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:07:45.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
10:07:52.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profile climb
10:08:01.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 2
10:11:08.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
10:11:24.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:12:06.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
10:12:17.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing at 1000 ft/min
10:14:17.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through cloud
10:14:20.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
10:15:05.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p2 start of p3
10:15:12.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
10:20:11.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:20:26.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p 3 start of p 4 profile climb
10:24:52.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** over lad
10:25:56.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3000 ft
10:26:00.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** over land
10:26:15.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:16.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:17.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:18.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:19.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:26:20.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:12.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:13.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:14.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:14.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:36:15.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:36:16.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:37:19.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
10:40:49.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:50.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:52.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:53.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:53.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:54.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:40:56.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:40:57.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:00.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:01.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:02.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:03.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:34.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
10:48:41.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
10:49:05.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:49:34.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
10:51:52.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
10:52:31.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
10:54:03.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:04.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:05.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:06.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:54:07.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:54:07.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:55:56.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
10:59:09.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of sawtooth profile
11:06:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:46.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:47.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:47.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:06:48.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:49.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:07:06.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing sawtooth
11:08:32.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
11:16:37.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
11:18:05.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
11:18:17.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:18:49.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:21:04.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
11:21:18.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:18.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:20.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:21.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:21.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:21:22.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:21:50.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:23:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:25:41.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** going up to 4500 ft
11:31:30.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
11:31:35.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4500ft
11:32:01.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:33:05.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:35:17.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
11:36:04.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:38:02.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:42:23.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
11:43:33.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:34.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:35.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:36.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:37.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:37.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:39.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:39.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:40.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:41.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:42.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:43.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:45:00.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
11:45:24.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:46:19.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:46:44.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** passing through cloud
11:49:06.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
11:49:25.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
11:50:24.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
11:50:52.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:52:17.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
11:59:08.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
11:59:32.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
12:00:17.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:03:02.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
12:03:23.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:03:28.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:29.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:30.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:31.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:32.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:33.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:35.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:36.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:38.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:39.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:03:40.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:03:40.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:05:50.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
12:13:30.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
12:14:40.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:17:38.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** 9 deg
12:17:49.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

12:17:50.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:51.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:52.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:17:53.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:17:54.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:18:27.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:18:47.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:19:08.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb from 500 ft to 10000 ft
12:20:09.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
12:24:52.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** now above clouds
12:28:31.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
12:29:07.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
12:29:37.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:38.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:39.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:40.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:41.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:42.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:44.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:45.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:46.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:47.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:29:48.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:29:49.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:30:22.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8 deg
12:30:51.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile climb and end of science
12:32:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:28.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:29.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:30.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:31.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:32:32.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:32:33.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B406

Date: 25/09/08

Instruments

1. Condensation running down inside of RF camera window.
2. Video PC crashed
3. Heimann not calibrating properly

CVI -

Neph -PSAP -

SWS -

SHIMS -

AMS / SP2 -

Core Chem -

Cloud physics -

FWVS,

TAFTS,

AVAPS,

ARIES,

MARSS,

DEIMOS

Aircraft

ISDN Emails

MPDS

Run for approx 3 hours

Satcom-H Calls

Issues

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B406:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Megan Northway
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
AMS / SP2 log	AMS / SP2 log operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log sheet has been provided so far for this flight

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	11 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following video recordings in avi format should be available at the BADC :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_085218_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_095218_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_105218_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_115218_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_085210_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_095210_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_105210_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_115210_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_085204_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_095204_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_105204_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_115204_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_085213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_095213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_105213_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080925_r0_b406_115213_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.